

INTEGRATING TECHNIQUES TO INCREASE THE SPEAKING ABILITY OF CEFR B1 LEVEL LEARNERS IN EFL CLASSES

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ABSTRACT

The research examined the effectiveness of multimedia presentation, role play and debate in improving CEFR B1 level EFL learners' speaking skills. Two-group experimental research design helped to collect data among higher class pupils. A questionnaire helped to study the opinions of English teachers of Uzbek public schools in Tashkent. The duration of treatment contained five months, three lessons in a week. The outcomes demonstrated that the p -value= <0.001 was less than .05, exactly, which means the difference between the two groups' achievement was statistically significant. The groups yielded a small effect size. Cohen's $d=2.178$ for experimental was slightly higher than the other group (Cohen's $s=1,769$). The limitation of the study depends on controlling time in the process of utilizing three techniques in a lesson. The research concluded integrating techniques to improve the speaking skills of EFL learners who have different learning styles in the CEFR context.

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the learning process has been prior than teaching language. Improving learners' communicative ability has a significant role as linguistic competence. Speaking ability includes the range of lexeme, grammar competence, correct pronunciation, and coherence in meaning. Furthermore, one method is not enough for all learners to have different learning styles. In this situation, a teacher can integrate some speaking teaching methods such as Pole play, Multimedia Presentation and Debate by following the time management of the lesson.

Most linguists and EFL teachers suggested interactive ways of teaching to learning speak in English as a foreign language. Communicative Language teaching and collaboration are the best choices for this aim. Dangerfield (1991) believes that students can practice optimum speaking level in a limited time through role play. Moreover, the method provides students with a chance to get better. According to Ladousse (1992), role play is a communicative technique that develops language students' fluency, interaction and motivation. Furthermore, communicative activities encourage

learners to negotiate for meaning. The interview has a significant effect on language mastery (Rakab, 2016).

Speaking is one of the necessary skills to be learned by language learners to express thoughts and feelings, communicate and gain information. Many linguists and psychologists have explored typical approaches, methods, techniques to enhance the speaking capability of EFL learners. However, Role play, Multimedia Presentation, and Debate techniques have not been integrated to teach language learners. Therefore, the study aimed to find responses to the following questions:

1. To what extent does the integration of three teaching methods work well to develop the speaking skills of CEFR B1 level learners in EFL classes?
2. Are there any significant differences between the speaking skills of participants after the treatment in comparison to previous knowledge?

BACKGROUND AND RATIONALLY OF THE STUDY

Role of the speaking skill

Human are creatures who can communicate, exchange ideas, feelings and recognize other nations. People have been learning a foreign language for different purposes. English as an international language has a vital position in many parts of our life. Learning the English language, especially, speaking creates an opportunity to communicate with other people globally and study or continue their education abroad. Whilst reading and listening are the two receptive skills in language acquisition and usage, writing and speaking are the two productive skills that

must incorporate in successful communication. According to Zaremba (2006), Speaking is the most vital of the four main English abilities necessary for communication. Effective oral communication generally results in advantages for both presenters and corporate organizations. He also mentioned the research that found speaking abilities and communication skills required over work experience, motivation, and academic credentials as criteria for new job recruitment. Students who study English as a foreign language (EFL) have few opportunities to speak English outside the classroom. Few opportunities to interact with English speakers or members of the international community.

Despite many teaching methods, both teacher and learner faced difficulties choosing successful techniques. As a productive skill, speaking involves utilizing speech to deliver meaning to others (Spratt, Pulvernes, & Williams, 2005). Therefore, teachers should pay attention to a particular aspect of speaking, e.g. pronunciation, fluency, grammatical accuracy. It is a little complicated to train all aspects jointly and regularly during a lesson. At this time, it can be beneficial to mix short versions of multimedia presentations, interview-based pole play and read and listen methods.

Multimedia Presentation

Multimedia Presentation expresses such aspects in teaching foreign languages: creating an active condition to utilize modern IT and increasing quality of teaching speaking skills (Lazereva, A. C., 2007); teaching vocabulary-oriented foreign language communication (Kichenko, A. A., 2010); make easy the

meaning of the text (Zubov, A. V., Zubova, I.I., 2009). Additionally, visual data demonstrated by the presentation are attractive, memorable, persuasive that help pupils keep hectic learning procedures during the lesson. In their study, Tatiana Bachina, Juliya Ageeva, Victoria Vlasicheva mentioned that "... educational potential of presentations does not only make the class interesting increasing motivation for students but, it has substantial prospect to teach speech habits and skills.

Due to visual and audial aids, Mayer (2001) stated multimedia as a combination of texts, images, sounds, and videos into the integrated multi-sensory interactive tool to express a message or information to an audience. As a result, it creates a positive atmosphere for the learner to revise their work, lots of the visuals demonstrate their ideas, critically overcome the problem working in a group. Moreover, Lue (2003) and Andi Tenri Ampa (2013) noted that Multimedia Presentation enhances pupils' cognitive skills, for example, concentrating, date collecting, memorizing, constructing, analyzing, generalizing and assessing.

Role Play

One of the activities which student practice their speaking skills through saying and doing is Role Play. It helps teachers to create positive English-speaking atmosphere. The reason of involving physical activeness in classes Role Play encourage students to learn foreign language effectively. Dorathy and Mahalakshmi (2011) and Mustafa Altun (2015) mentioned that role gives students an opportunity to practice communicating in different social context. According to Conforme and Torres (2013) role play help learners to gather new knowledge with

entertainment, amusement. Waffa (2014) stressed the importance of role play that learners sort out needed lexemes and coherent expressions to the role in the process of organizing activity, boosting participants' creativity and critical thinking through collaborative learning routines. About role play technique Kusnierek (2015) said that it is increase learners' interaction, motivation, learning, and teacher-student responsibilities (p.7).

Debate

A debate is one of the speaking techniques based on opposing viewpoints expressed and argued on a topic (Dale & Wolf, 2000).

Furthermore, it is an activity that different sides of the problem which discussed and defended in mini-groups of students. Learners practice their speaking skills spontaneously under the pressure of opposite sides in a limited time. In his study Bellon (2000) cited the benefits of the debate technique for language learners. A debate technique improves students' critical thinking, communication and question skills during the discussion.

Practically, most teachers choose the debate technique as a post-activity to train language skills. In this way, they can evaluate students' knowledge and activeness at the end of the lesson. Additionally, it is easy to revise the whole class positively through debate. One of the advantages is that the technique supports learners to work on critical thinking, self-confidence, feeling free while communicating, encouraging them to learn the language.

CEFR assessment criteria and B1 level specification for speaking

Common European Framework of Reference for Languages: Learning Teaching, Assessment (CEFR) is a program created by the Council of Europe (Common European Framework for Languages, Learning, Teaching, Assessment, 2001). J.J. Jalolov, G.T. Makhamova, Sh.S. Ashurova (2015) mentioned CEFR in the book "English Language Teaching Methodology".

The function of the document was to provide a basis for the elaboration of language syllabuses, curricula, guidelines, examinations and course books across Europe and provided a method of assessing and teaching applied to all modern languages in Europe.

According to CEFR assessment criteria, learner levels have six stages from A1 to C1, and all have names and descriptions for each skill and subskills. Every degree of CEFR and descriptors adapted to the social context of Uzbekistan, especially to each stage, aim and objectives, etc. Accounting for the CEFR, level expresses in the FLT content and requirements to the levels FLT. Based on the steps and levels of EFL, 10th and 11th-grade learners, academic lyceums, and vocational colleges should be B1 as to the original CEFR document.

The assessment of speaking contains five aspects. These are range, accuracy, fluency, interaction and coherence. The general level description says, "B1 level learners can keep going even though pausing for grammatical and lexical planning. And repair may be very evident as well as can link discrete, simple elements into a connected sequence to describe a variety of familiar subjects within their predictable situations."

(Cambridge ESOL's Main Suite exams, 2009).

METHODOLOGY

Two - group Experimental Research Designs is appropriate to define the effectiveness of the three integrated technique in a lesson to enhance the speaking skills of B1 learners. Due to collecting data on the study, the researcher will take hold of questionnaire among 16 EFL teachers of public school and the randomly selected A (experimental) and B (traditional) group pupils of 10th and 11th grades.

The experimental group was taught three techniques in a lesson a week for five months. Multimedia Presentation was used as a pre-activity to provide the learner with new information, enrich the vocabulary and give examples of how to pronounce words through listening to authentic audio and video materials attached presentation. Role-Play as a while service to strengthen new knowledge and speaking ability by interaction and communication. Debate, which is beneficial to communicational skills and critical thinking in the target language, promotes the pupils to conclude the theme and gain knowledge at the end of the lesson.

The researcher took a pre-test to clarify the current knowledge of the two groups before the treatment and noted the results. At the end of the experiment, the teacher took a post-test to define the effect of the methods. Three answers the question activities check learners speaking skills, 1) learners introduce themselves through answering teachers' questions. 2)

Choose a question card to describe a given situation. 3) answer questions on global issues (observing learners' critical thinking and problem-solving ability).

Learners knowledge was assessed according to CEFR speaking assessment criteria that adapted from CEFR official document such as a) range- 2, b) fluency-3 c) accuracy-2 d) interaction-1 e)

Paired Samples T-Test (Group A)

Measure 1	Measure 2	t	df	p	Cohen's d
post-test	- pre -test_speaking_group A	8.149	13	<.001	2.178

coherence-2 as for a result, a participant can collect a totally of 10 points.

Table 1

Table 2

Paired Samples T-Test (Group B)

Measure1	Measure 2	t	df	p	Cohen's d
post-test	- pre-test_Speaking Group B	6.618	13	<.001	1.769

Independent Samples T-Test findings of Two Groups' post-test result. This kind t-

test is used to analyze the differences between two groups.

Table 3

Independent Samples T-Test

	t	df	p	Cohen's d
Speaking Test Achievement	4.241	26	<.001	1.603

Table 4

Group Descriptives

	Group	N	Mean	SD	SE
Speaking Test Achievement	Group A	14	8.100	0.562	0.150
	Group B	14	7.186	0.579	0.155

RESULT AND DISSCUSION

Two types of T-tests in the JASP dataset reported the findings of Two-group experimental research design. Firstly, upshots of pre-test and post-test required comparison in each group. In the

second step, consequences defined to what extent the treatments give fruit? And was there any difference between teaching ways?

Paired Samples T-test demonstrated the degree of effectiveness in comparing

pre-test and post-test scores. Results showed that improvement exists in both groups speaking skills according to the scores of results. In Tables 1 and 2, it was clear that $p\text{-value} = <0.001$ was less than .05, exactly, the diversity of groups enhanced was statistically significant. However, the productiveness of speaking teaching methods was higher in the experimental group because Cohen's equals 2.178 in comparing the traditional group's findings on effect size (Cohen's = 1.769).

Independent Samples T-Test expressed the outcomes of two different groups. As far the findings, $p\text{-value} = <0.001$ was less than .05 meant the difference was statistically significant. Cohen's $d=1.6$ meant a small effect size. Minimum and maximum scores of A B groups were diverse after the post-test: Group A=7;9 Group B=6.5;8.1. Test of normality showed slightly higher results ($p=A/0.9$; $B/0.1$) than .05 meant the data was in a norm. In short, all discussions informed that integrating techniques was valuable to increase B1 level EFL learners' speaking ability.

CONCLUSION

Based on the result of the experiment, it concluded that integrating Multimedia presentation, Role play and Debate works positively to improve the speaking skills of CEFR B1 level learners. The integration increases the motivation of EFL learners to keep learning not only speaking skills but also the whole language competence. It helps to widen the critical thinking and train more the speaking ability in real conversation. The combination of techniques is productive for all types of learners. Because they can watch, listen and do in acquiring new knowledge.

However, nothing is perfect that there is a limitation in the mixed implementation of three techniques in a lesson. It is time management. It requires teachers to use a shorter version to cover all of them in class time for school learners.

As a researcher, I suggest that the other educators effectively utilize Multimedia Presentation, Role play and Debate techniques to develop speaking skills. I hope the study will be favourable for both teachers and learners in their educational procedure.

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